

WORKING TITLE: Pupillary and cardiac signatures of social-affective inference in individuals with subclinical negative symptoms.

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Notes about this analysis plan:

Data acquisition has been completed at the time of writing this analysis plan. That is because we were not able to acquire as much data as originally planned and the study was stopped prematurely due to circumstances outside of our control.

This also meant that we change our approach to the analyses slightly by adding analyses. While the study had been aimed at a sample size with sufficient power for group comparisons (N=82), the final sample size may be too small for that (N=44).

However, all data, including behavioural and physiological data has not been analysed yet and modeling has not been completed at the time of uploading this analysis plan. While this does not constitute a pre-registration per se, we still believe pre-defining the exact analyses that will be done prior to data processing and analysis has merit. Just as we would with a timelier preregistration any deviations from this analysis plan will be described in the manuscript as post-hoc analyses.

Study Design and Tasks

Forty-Four participants from the general population who scored on opposite ends (N=22 in each group) of the constricted affect dimension of an updated Schizotypal Personality Questionnaire (SPQ; Raine, 1991; Wuthrich & Bates, 2005) were invited to complete two novel social-affective inference tasks and a control task. In the first task, the Social Affective Prediction task (SAP), participants had to smile at faces when they predicted that the face would smile back at them on a given trial. Participants interacted with three faces with different inherent probabilities to smile back. Participants' task was to learn these probabilities. Congruent participant-face affect (smile/smile or no smile/no smile) resulted in a point for participants, incongruent participant-face affect (smile/ no smile or no smile/smile) resulted in a point deduction. In the first 42 trials of the 120 trials of the task participants received smiles 80% of the time, then this switched to less smiles and then changed again toward more smiles toward the end. The second task was a control task for the SAP task (SAPC) and was designed exactly the same way as the SAP task but instead of predicting smiles, participants had to predict whether an egg would be spoiled or fresh. The third task they played was the Affective Approach Avoid (AAA) task where participants were asked to learn about two faces' propensities to respond positively to being approached. More specifically, participants were instructed that they will be interacting with two individuals (faces) in the task, one of which will be more happy to be approached than the other. This would be indicated with a "happy" tone (an Instagram notification sound) or a negative tone (windows error message sound). They were also informed that there will be phases during which the more approachable person may be less happy to be approached or vice-versa, the less "socially inclined" person would be more happy to be approached. Their task was to predict when and what face would react positively to being approached. If they approached a face that responded with a positive tone, they earned a point. If they avoided a face that would have given them a negative tone when approached, they earned a point. Incongruent actions and responses lead to the loss of points. Notably, participants only received feedback from the face if they approached the face. When they avoided, the face became smaller and no feedback was issued. However, they still lost or gained a point based on whether it was the correct decision.

Background

Jeganathan & Breakspear (2021) propose that patients with negative symptoms cannot rely on information coming from their bodies when making inference about other individuals socio-affective reactions to the patients' affective actions. As a consequence, individuals will disengage from these social-affective interactions (subconsciously) which would over time lead to blunted affect.

Distress about one's own symptoms has been shown to be increased in high-risk for psychosis populations and to diminish again over the course of the clinical trajectory (Wilson et al., 2020). From a Bayesian inference perspective, being distressed about one's symptoms may be related to increased precision assigned to sensory input that is related to the symptom (i.e. social-affective stimuli), which leads to higher weighting of PEs, and thus more but maladaptive updating. Furthermore, high distress about one's symptoms in conjunction with high frequency of the symptom would imply that individuals experience these PEs a lot in everyday life.

We will investigate how distress about one's negative symptoms as well as frequency and distress as a composite (taking into account the frequency of symptoms as well) impact individuals' learning in the tasks described above and how cardiac and pupillary signals differentially predict learning.

It has been shown that **heart rate (HR)** slowing increased when anticipated outcomes have high valence and are negative and uncertain (Kastner et al., 2017; Poli et al., 2007). In our task that would correspond to the negative outcome tone in the AAA task and to the non-smile outcomes in the SAP task, especially when participants' associated precision-weight is high due to low belief precision. HR recovery after the stimulus (or in our case outcome) has been shown to be prolonged after negative and informative outcomes and faster after positive outcomes (Crone et al., 2005; Kastner et al., 2017). In the SAP task the smile outcome in response to a non-smile (i.e. a wrong prediction) would be both positive and informative while the smile outcome in response to a smile would be positive but not informative. And the non-smile outcomes are somewhat negative and can be similarly grouped into informative and non-informative. If we predict that individuals scoring high on the blunted affect measure of the SPQ find signals from the body unhelpful for social-affective inference, we would expect to see the above-mentioned relationships in the low-scorer but not the high-scorer group.

Pupil dilation (vs. constriction) in response to stimuli in cognitive tasks is related to processing information, i.e. processing sensory input (Colizoli et al., 2026; McGovern, 2024). Thus, precision being allocated to sensory input should be positively related to pupil dilation.

We will thus investigate how pupil dilation as a response to outcomes is related to pwPEs.

Main Research Questions

RQ01: Are heart rate and pupil dilation less related to learning in individuals with **constricted affect** (based on a self-report measurement)?

RQ02: Is this relationship **specific to social-affective inference**?

RQ03: How does **distress about one's negative symptoms** influence social-affective inference and how is this reflected in both the heart rate and pupil dilation reactivity in these tasks.

Modelling

For the AAA task we will use a categorical Hierarchical Gaussian Filter (HGF) model to model learning in conjunction with a response model that takes into account participants' choices and the information gain one choice would result in vs. the other. For the SAP and SAPC task we will use a categorical HGF with a response model for binary responses.

Models will be implemented in Julia

(<https://computationalpsychiatry.github.io/HierarchicalGaussianFiltering.jl/>)

The HGF models learning about the predictability of the faces (two in the AAA task and three on the SAP and SAPC task) on the second level using two or three categorical nodes respectively and models environmental uncertainty (stochasticity across the task) using a unifying "volatility" parent on the second level, which governs learning of each category on the second level. This allows us to extract both belief precisions and pwPEs for each participant on each trial.

We will report parameter recovery results and posterior predictive tests (Hess et al., 2024).

Statistics

We will use Bayesian statistical models using the BRMS R package to analyse our data. Because the PE traces are interdependent, we will model an additional autocorrelation component in the model. We will interpret effects with $BF_{10} / BF_{01} \geq 5$ and conduct and interpret post-hoc tests if we should find evidence for an effect in a repeated measures design. We will report model-averaged R^2 .

AAA Task

First, we will extract **inter-beat-intervals** (IBIs) after stimulus and before outcome presentation ($IBI_{pre-Outcome}$) and IBIs after outcome presentation ($IBI_{after-Outcome}$) for all tasks and calculate the median of both pre- and after-outcome IBIs for each participant and each event (AAA task: all approach trials, all trials).

We will extract trial-by-trial baseline-corrected pupil dilation data after outcome presentation and calculate the median of for each participant and each event (all approach trials, all trials).

We will first test whether individuals' precisions pwPEs and belief precisions are less related to inter-beat-intervals (IBIs) after stimulus and before outcome presentation as a function of group in the **AAA task** (RQ01).

We then conduct the following models for group comparisons:

Analysis model PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{allApproachTrials}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, allApproachTrials}$
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model pre-outcome:

Dependent variable: belief precision_{all trials}
Independent variables: $IBI_{pre-Outcome, all trials}$
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

We will test whether negative symptom distress and negative symptom total score covary with the relationships between HR indices and learning quantities (pwPEs and belief precisions) (RQ03).

Analysis model PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{allApproachTrials}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, allApproachTrials}$
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model pre-outcome:

Dependent variable: belief precision_{all trials}
Independent variables: $IBI_{pre-Outcome, all trials}$
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

We will further investigate how pupil dilation relates to pwPEs as a function of group (RQ01) in the AAA task.

Analysis model model PEs:

Dependent variable: pwPEs_{allApproachTrials}
Independent variable: pupil dilation_{allApproachTrials}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

We will test whether negative symptom distress and negative symptom total score covary with the relationships between pupil dilation and learning quantities (pwPEs and belief precisions) (RQ03).

Analysis model negative PEs:

Dependent variable: pwPEs_{allApproachTrials}
Independent variable: pupil dilation_{allApproachTrials}
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

SAP vs SAPC Task

We will then test whether the above relationships are specific to social-affective inference by comparing the **SAP** and **SAPC task** (RQ02).

We will conduct the following analysis models for **group comparisons**:

Analysis model negative PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{negativePEs}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, negativePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model positive PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{positivePEs}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, positivePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model pre-outcome:

Dependent variable: $belief\ precision_{all\ trials}$
Independent variables: $IBI_{pre-Outcome, all\ trials}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model negative PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{negativePEs}$
Independent variable: $pupil\ dilation_{negativePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model positive PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{positivePEs}$
Independent variable: $pupil\ dilation_{positivePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Grouping Variable: {High scorers, low scorers}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

We will conduct the following analysis models to relate outcomes to **negative symptoms distress** scores:

Analysis model negative PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{PEs, negativePEs}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, negativePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model positive PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{positivePEs}$
Independent variable: $IBI_{after-Outcome, positivePEs}$
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model pre-outcome:

Dependent variable: belief precision_{all trials}
Independent variables: $IBI_{pre-Outcome, all trials}$
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model negative PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{PEs, negativePEs}$
Independent variable: pupil dilation_{negativePEs}
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age

Analysis model positive PEs:

Dependent variable: $pwPEs_{positivePEs}$
Independent variable: pupil dilation_{positivePEs}
Repeated measures Factor: Task {SAP, SAPC}
Covariate of interest: negative symptoms distress score
Covariate of no interest (added to the null model): gender, age